

Obeah in Jamaica, British Guiana, and Barbados, 1760-1834

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Entry tags: Caribbean Religion, Religious Group, (Afro-)Caribbean religions, Subaltern Religion, Language, African Religion, English

Obeah denotes African-derived spiritual and healing practices within the British Caribbean. While there is considerable argument over the specific origins of the word, it is generally agreed that it arose from one or more West African languages and the term has been used for centuries. More recently, obeah is sometimes conflated with a number of Afro-Caribbean religious and spiritual practices, but within this study it deals with its original meaning within the British Caribbean during slavery. Among its many applications, obeah has been used in healing physical and mental illnesses, causing harm to enemies or rivals, protection from harm from disease or physical assault, and with finding a wrong-doer within a community. Although there may be some argument over whether it is a religion, it was a well-known spiritual practice and healing modality among bondpeople in the British Caribbean. Studies of obeah have linked it to specific African practices, particularly from West Africa where most enslaved people or their ancestors in the British Caribbean originated. It was distinctly Afro-Caribbean up until emancipation, after which evidence shows that in some areas such as Trinidad, indentured servants from India added aspects. While undoubtedly originating before the dates discussed here, it came under the scrutiny of British and other European colonists when specific incidents such as Tacky's Revolt in Jamaica linked the practice to slave rebellion, resulting in legal Acts outlawing it. Practiced throughout the British Caribbean, the three areas considered here, Barbados, Jamaica, and British Guiana (Guyana), have been the sources of the greatest amount of documentation studied. In that regard, it needs to be noted that the information gleaned from these documents is from the viewpoint of white settlers and government officials in Britain, and not those of the enslaved people of African origin, whose testimonies, where available, were usually taken under duress. However, much effort has been made by scholars in recent years to read between the lines and compare documented cases to learn as much as possible about the practices during these years. Obeah use is still in evidence, although it is technically illegal in some places, and like other spiritual practices, it has evolved over the centuries. In past centuries, it was considered by white observers to be a by-word for backwardness and primitivity, and has appeared in novels as a source of fear, or used on the gullible. In recent years, it has begun to be known as an Afro-Caribbean tradition that encompasses a variety of spiritual and religious characteristics worthy of serious study.

Date Range: 1760 CE - 1834 CE

Region: Caribbean including Jamaica, Barbados, and Guyana

Region tags: Caribbean, British Guiana, Jamaica, Barbados

Barbados, British Guiana, Jamaica within the British Caribbean, 1650-1833

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Paton, Diana. "The Cultural Politics of Obeah: Religion, Colonialism and Modernity in the Caribbean World" (Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press, 2015)
- Source 2: Murrell, Nathaniel Samuel. "Afro-Caribbean Religions: An Introduction to Their Historical, Cultural, and Sacred Traditions" (Philadelphia: Temple University Press, 2009)
- Source 3: Brown, Vincent. "Tacky's Revolt: The Story of an Atlantic Slave War" (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2020)

Notes: Paton's book covers obeah throughout its history into the 20th century. Murrell's book has a chapter specifically about obeah, but the entire book is helpful in its coverage of Afro-Caribbean religions. Brown's book references obeah throughout and it provides a detailed background of the importance of obeah in slave rebellions and the beginnings of legal action against the practice.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1080/14788810.2015.1025213>
- Source 1 Description: Gerbner, Katharine. "They call me Obea": German Moravian Missionaries and Afro-Caribbean Religion in Jamaica, 1754-1760,' "Atlantic Studies: Global Currents," Vol. 12, No. 2 (2015): 160-178
- Source 2 URL: <https://doi.org/10.1215/07990537-2008-002>
- Source 2 Description: Paton, Diana. 'Obeah Acts: Producing and Policing the Boundaries in the Caribbean,' "Small Axe," Vol. 13, No. 1 (2009): 1-18
- Source 3 URL: <https://doi.org/10.5309/willmaryquar.68.3.0451>
- Source 3 Description: Browne, Randy M. 'The "Bad Business" of Obeah: Power, Authority, and the Politics of Slave Culture in the British Caribbean,' "The William and Mary Quarterly, Vol. 68, No. 3 (2011): 451-480.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://slaveryandfreedomlaws.lib.unb.ca/laws/jamaica-1760>
- Source 1 Description: An Act to remedy the Evils arising from irregular Assemblies of Slaves, and to prevent their possessing Arms and Ammunition and going from Place to Place without Tickets
- Source 2 URL: <https://slaveryandfreedomlaws.lib.unb.ca/laws/barbados-1819>
- Source 2 Description: An Act for the better Prevention of the Practice of Obeah.
- Source 3 URL: <https://lawcat.berkeley.edu/record/418644>
- Source 3 Description: Trial of a slave in Berbice, for the crime of obeah and murder : proceedings of the Court of Criminal Justice of the Colony Berbice, on the trial of the Negro Willem, alias Sara, alias Cuffey, for murder of the Negress Madalon : and also the trials of the Negroes Primo, Mey, Kees, and Corydon, for aiding and abetting in said murder.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Christian missionaries attempted to turn enslaved people away from obeah.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– No

Notes: Obeah was perceived as sorcery and anti-Christian, while enslaved people often had profound respect for obeah.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: See above answers.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Obeah practitioners could be executed, exiled, severely flogged, or kept in chains. Obeah was sometimes used by bondspeople during times of rebellion to protect themselves from whites or to cause harm.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: It should be noted that people were not actually "assigned" to obeah as a spiritual practice. Rather, those who sought the help of a practitioner made contact with one and negotiated payment for a service.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: This is a qualified "yes" in that adherents/practitioners were either enslaved or had been enslaved.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: Anyone could seek the help of a practitioner. Although the majority of "obeahmen" were male, there were numerous "obeahwomen" as well.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Practitioners seemed to become a practicing obeahman/obeahwoman through being taught by another after displaying a propensity toward the practice..

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Notes: It was generally illegal after the Jamaica passed a law against it in 1760 and other areas in the British Caribbean followed suit. See 1760 law in primary Sources above. See also Chapter 1 in Paton, "The Cultural Politics of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It was a clandestine activity and illegal to practice, therefore it is not known how many people took part in rituals or how many obeahmen and women there were. Usually a bondsperson or persons

would go to an obeah practitioner to seek help in overcoming illness or a certain situation, or to cause harm to a rival. See, for example, Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above re population.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (not related to larger religious group)

Notes: Afro-Caribbean spiritual practice engaged in by some enslaved people.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Scholarship seems to agree that there were individual "obeahmen" and women who worked independently for individuals or groups.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– Yes

Notes: Much remains unknown regarding the precise nature of powers associated with obeah practitioners due to its clandestine activity and the enslaved status of those who used it. For considerations on the powers of practitioners, see Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in past lives:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Powers are acquired by individual deeds carried out in the current life:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Practitioners engaged in various rituals and led others through them to bring about the desired outcome. It was understood that certain individuals had the talent or gift of achieving this through a knowledge of various herbs, incantations, and movements, but whether their powers were acquired through related rituals is unknown.

↳ Powers are inherited:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from a supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes" as details are not available; however, see Wray, John, and Rain, Thomas. *The Life and Labours of John Wray, Pioneer Missionary in British Guiana, Compiled Chiefly From His Own Mss. and Diaries*. London: John Snow & Co., 1892: 113 where an accused obeahman states that he acquired his powers from "good spirits."

↳ Powers are culturally transmitted from another human (e.g. teacher):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Powers are associated with leadership office they assume:

– No

Notes: Qualified "no" in that there is no evidence of such and, from all accounts, it seems that practitioners were not "leaders" in that they held office. However, they were able to lead others in rituals in order to bring about a specific outcome. For a detailed account, see Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unknown (see notes regarding leadership above). It appears that obeahmen and women come to their status over time and practice.

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As with other aspects of obeahmen and women, much is unknown due to the enslaved status of practitioners and followers.

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See above. There is evidence of argument with practitioners. See, for example, Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unlikely.

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There is no evidence of such and it is unlikely that there were sacred sites given the descriptions of obeahmen and women bringing their practice to those who requested it and the nature of enslavement.

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: See above answer regarding specific sites.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes" in that no specific explanations of belief are available. However, trance states were common and it therefore seems likely. See, for example, Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: Qualified "yes." See above answer.

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The answer to this is uncertain due to lack of documentation. However, due to the belief in spirit possession and indications of African ancestor veneration, it seems likely. See Murrell, "African Caribbean Religions," Chapter 6, cited in Sources.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Unlikely given the clandestine nature of the practice and the adherents' enslaved status. Generally treated as other enslaved people. A caveat to this answer is that death could happen during or as the result of an illegal ritual, necessitating hiding a corpse to escape detection by authorities, as described in Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: See above answer.

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: See answer under Special Treatment of Corpses.

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Due to clandestine nature and the illegality of practicing obeah. See answer under Special Treatment of Corpses.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– I don't know

Notes: Specific beings not generally known of, but there are many aspects of the supernatural in rituals such as trance possession and the practice of a ritual known as the Minje Mama dance which was related to an African water spirit or goddess. For more information, see any of the printed or on-line sources cited above. For further information on supernatural aspects, see: de Barros, Juanita, "Setting things right": Medicine and magic in British Guiana, 1803-38,' "Slavery & Abolition" Vol. 25, No. 1 (2004): 28-50: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144039042000220919>

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Details unknown. For West African related beliefs, see de Barros, <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144039042000220919> noted above.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Obeah could be used to "punish" an enemy or rival, but it is unclear how this was believed to work - whether it was the action of a supernatural being or some other supernatural phenomena.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: As with supernatural punishment, it is unclear how this was believed to work - whether the action of a supernatural being or some other supernatural phenomena.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such. Obeah, as a practice, could heal or harm, depending on the will of the practitioner and the person or persons they were working for.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory

painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No evidence of such for practitioners. However, this is a qualified "no" in that wounds could sometimes be inflicted on a person as a part of their spiritual "healing." Apparently it was usual that these were slight, there are examples of more severe wounding. See, for example, Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: Although evidence does not point to a requirement of "sacrifice", death could happen accidentally during ritual and as the result of severe beating. See, for example, Browne, "The 'Bad Business' of Obeah" cited in Sources, wherein a woman died as a result of beating and torturing her to remove the "bad story" that was causing harm to the community.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: As payment to the practitioner or the sacrifice of animals such as a cock as part of ritual. See, for example, de Barros, "'Setting things right': Medicine and magic in British Guiana, 1803-38," 1: <https://doi.org/10.1080/0144039042000220919> cited under Supernatural Beings.

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– I don't know

Other:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: Not on a regular basis. During rituals for specific outcomes the group expected to attend.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: Being a part of obeah rituals or practice was an extreme risk in that it was illegal and could result in severe punishment, including execution. See Paton, "The Cultural Politics of Obeah" cited in Sources.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Notes: None known for a practitioner, and any member of the community could hire them.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– Yes

Notes: See answers regarding illegality of practice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Obeah rituals were usually community-based, but some were larger than others.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: This varied depending on circumstances. For the most part unknown of due to the illegality of rituals.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There was no set time for regular rituals.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– Yes

Notes: Alcohol, specifically rum, was often involved.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: No evidence of such.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: While technically belonging within colonies of the British Empire, the group who practiced

obeah and engaged with its practitioners were enslaved. They were from various areas of West Africa, or their near ancestors were.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: As adherents were enslaved and engaged primarily in agriculture in a plantation society, famine would affect the whole colony.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Notes: Group made up of enslaved persons who were already impoverished.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Group made up of enslaved persons.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Notes: Qualified "no" in that for the general enslaved population on plantations there was a "sick house" where they were to receive care. In reality, very little care was usually given. Most enslaved people did not live into old age in the colonies described.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: See above answer.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: At various times and locations Christian missionaries provided education to the enslaved. This form of education could be precarious in that slaveholders often tried to stop the education of bondspeople, fearing that it would lead to rebellion.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: There was not a bureaucracy, as such. There was a obeahman or woman who practiced the art and supplicants went to them to request assistance for various problems. However, in some cases "drivers", bondspeople who kept order and saw that work was completed among the enslaved, would go to a practitioner to request aid for the general population of bondspeople in times of trouble or illness.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Being enslaved, adherents had to interact with governmental institutions, depending on their position. Some bondspeople worked directly for the government in various capacities.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Notes: Not directly, but some enslaved people would be required to work on water management as part of their usual tasks.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the

religious group in question:

– I don't know

Notes: This could depend on the specific location in a given colony.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: Some enslaved people could, however, provide transportation as required by slaveholders.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The practice of obeah was illegal and they could be captured and imprisoned prior to trial by a police force or military.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The practice of obeah was illegal and the penalties imposed by the government judicial systems

were harsh.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Not as an official institution. They frequently engaged in acts that could be perceived as punishment, such as flogging. These were commonly meant to remove harmful spirits or ill luck from the recipient, however, and not meant exactly as "punishment."

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Notes: Not specifically.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– No

Notes: Qualified "no" as generally the obeah practitioner and followers were bondspeople who did not have much, if any, property to seize. The emphasis was on severe corporal punishment, including execution in some cases.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The laws of England and the government of the colony.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: Not an institutionalized military, but during times of rebellion, obeah could play an important part in creating solidarity and beliefs of immunity from the weapons of government military and militia. For an important example of this, see Brown, Vincent. "Tacky's Revolt: The Story of an Atlantic Slave War" (Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 2020) The events surrounding this revolt resulted in the first law specifically against the practice of obeah.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: During times of insurgency, bondspeople, including those who practiced obeah, were subject to the regular military and the local militia.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If the adherents were also part of a group who received education through Christian missionaries or other source.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: If they were literate.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: Adherents would use the same calendar based on the Julian calendar as other Western groups.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The same Julian-based calendar was used throughout the Western world.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Gathering
- Fishing
- Pastoralism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: As those who participated in obeah were enslaved, the amount of food they could provide for themselves would vary, depending on what was available to them. In some colonies bondspeople were provided with provision grounds whereby they could grow and raise their own food, using any excess for trade. If allowed, they could fish or engage in gathering, if possible. Being primarily employed on large plantations, they were actively engaged in food production in general. However, many enslaved people were not given the time necessary to look after their provision grounds. Food would be provided by slaveholders, but often not enough or of sufficient variety. For details of this system in Demerara (British Guiana) see da Costa, Emilia Viotti. "Crowns of Glory, Tears of Blood: The Demerara Slave Rebellion of 1823 (New York and Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1994): 3-85.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Fishing
- Patorialism
- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Being primarily employed on large plantations, bondspeople who practiced obeah were actively engaged in food production in general. However, many enslaved people were not given

the time necessary to look after their provision grounds. Food would be provided by slaveholders, but often not enough or of sufficient variety. The food provided could consist of plantains and dried or salted fish from other areas of the British Atlantic and sold to slaveholders as slave provisions. For details of this system in Demerara (British Guiana) see da Costa, Emilia Viotti. "Crowns of Glory, Tears of Blood": 3-85, cited above.